

Exploring the informal uses of mobile phones by health workers and managers in Uganda: A qualitative study

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1. Summary

This PhD project will explore how health workers and managers in the public healthcare system in Uganda creatively use mobile phones to support their work and overcome everyday work challenges. While there is already a large body of work evaluating formal digital health programmes, this research project will address an important gap by building our understanding of the bottom-up, informal, and creative deployment of digital technologies in healthcare. The project shall specifically: (1) explore the experiences of health workers and managers as they utilise mobile phones in their everyday work; (2) establish the unmet needs of health workers and managers that can be addressed by informal and innovative mobile phone use; and (3) investigate how health workers and managers manage issues related to equity, transparency, patient confidentiality, and documentation of clinical practice using mobile phones. The project will deploy qualitative methodologies including observations of health workers carrying out their daily activities and participating in online messaging groups, semi-structured interviews, and focus group discussions. As part of the Norwegian Research Council-funded mHEALTH-INNOVATE-project, this project will be supported by a multidisciplinary team from Makerere University, Uganda; the Norwegian Institute of Public Health; the University of Oslo, Norway; Western Norway, University of Applied Sciences; Norwegian University of Sciences and Technology; Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health, USA; the World Health Organization; and the Healthcare Information for All network (HIFA).

The project's outcomes are anticipated to among others include: a peer-reviewed article-based dissertation; research evidence for the healthcare system in Uganda and beyond; capacity building and grounding for the PhD candidate in health systems' strengthening which is critical for Uganda as a low- and middle-income country (LMIC).

2. Relevance

Through its focus on building our understanding of how health workers and managers in LMICs creatively use mobile phones to address challenges in the public healthcare system, the PhD project will have a broad target group. One target group will be researchers both in academic and non-academic settings, interested in understanding the impact of digital technologies on health in LMICs. The other target groups will be international, national, and regional policy-makers. The project will reach these groups by connecting, as explained further below (see 6. Dissemination and communication of results), to the larger mHEALTH-INNOVATE project's work-package that aim to translate research findings into policy advice.

Relevance and importance to society

The project has relevance to society at a national and global level. At the national level, the project is aligned with the Government of Uganda's Vision 2040, National Development Plan 2015/16-2019/20 (NDPII), and the Ministry of Health's national eHealth policy, which identify information, communication and technology as important to the strengthening of the health system and the transformation of health service delivery. Specifically, the project will provide evidence to policy-

makers, such as the Ministry of Health that may aid in the formalization and scaling-up of these innovative uses of mobile phones, in ways that improve service delivery.

Globally, the findings will be directly relevant to SDG3, especially target 3.C (“Increase health financing and support health workforce in developing countries”). Informing the effective adaptation of digital tools and strengthened health worker performance will also contribute to service delivery for other SDG3 sub-goals and ultimately the reduction of disease burden. The findings will support SDG9 on building resilient infrastructure and fostering innovation, and in particular the target on increasing access to ICT, which has substantial implications for health service delivery and health outcomes.

Compliance with strategic documents

This project is well aligned with the current Makerere University Strategic Plan 2016/2017- 2020/2021 which emphasizes the role of research evidence and multidisciplinary teams in the establishment of harmonized digital systems in Uganda.

3. Aspects relating to the research project

Background and status of knowledge

While there has been moderate progress in the development of health systems in some LMICs (McCool et al., 2022), health systems in many of these countries are still too weak to deliver high-quality services. Poor infrastructure at health facilities and a dearth of well-trained health workers are two important factors that hamper delivery of services (MoH, 2020). The few available health workers are often overwhelmed to meet the high demand for clinical, curative, preventive, mental, rehabilitative, or palliative services. This is a serious concern, especially in sub-Saharan Africa where trained and skilled health workers are estimated at only 3% of all the global health workforce (WHO, 2006). In Uganda, there is approximately one skilled health professional for every 1,000 inhabitants (MoH, 2020).

In 2019, the World Health Organization (WHO) published its first guidelines on the use of digital health strategies for health systems strengthening (WHO, 2019). These guidelines were informed by a series of Cochrane Reviews exploring the effectiveness, acceptability and feasibility of mobile phones for a range of tasks, including health worker training and decision-support, stock notification, and telemedicine (Agarwal et al., 2020). The reviews highlight a range of challenges when mobile phone-based strategies initiated by researchers, governments and others are implemented, and a need for new ideas about how these challenges can be overcome.

Since the WHO guidelines were published, access to low-cost mobile phones and to the internet has increased further. In addition, the Covid-19 pandemic has placed enormous pressure on health systems. Faced with these circumstances, health workers are increasingly using their mobile phones to develop their own strategies and solve the problems they face in their everyday work (Hampshire et al., 2021). This can include the use of messaging apps, such as Viber, Messenger, Telegram and WhatsApp, to communicate and provide support to one another. It can also include informal approaches to gathering, storing and sharing information including clinical or logistical data. These solutions could represent innovative strategies that formal health systems can learn from, but they could also create challenges of their own and warrant further exploration.

Digital technologies have been promoted as an important mechanism for enhancing workforce performance, advancing universal health coverage and other Sustainable Development Goal 3 (SDG3) targets (Heeks & Stanforth, 2015). The mobile telephone is today the most widely spread digital technology, providing access to information and services for communities. (Furuholt & Matotay, 2011).

Global estimates indicate that there are 8.3 billion active mobile phone subscriptions (approximately 1.08 per capita) of which 6.7 billion were held in LMICs (ITU, n.d.). As of March 2020, Uganda had 28.4 million subscriptions (NITA, 2018). However, these subscriptions are concentrated in urban populations and reflects a gender bias with 81.6% of males and 63.2% of females owning mobile phones (NITA, 2018, p. 130). As mobile telephone ownership increased, so too has internet connectivity (Namatovu & Kanjo, 2019). The Uganda Communication Commission report (UCC, 4th August 2022) indicates increased mobile phone connections from 31.2 million in March 2021 to 35 million in March 2022, representing an addition of 3.8 million subscribers. The increase in connectivity is a result of several factors, including the liberalizing of the telecommunication market, facilitating competition in Uganda, and the availability of more affordable smartphones from East Asia (UCC, 2022).

The increase in mobile subscriptions in LMICs, including in Uganda, has resulted in the growing digitalization of service delivery and utilization, including in healthcare, in a phenomenon that has been known as mobile health or mHealth. In Uganda, as well as in other African countries including Kenya, Malawi, Uganda, Zambia, and South Africa, mobile phones have supported health-related interventions in HIV/AIDs campaigns, family planning, malnutrition, sanitation, and hygiene (McCool et al., 2022). In extending the reach of health workers and medical services, mobiles have been instrumental in reducing the health personnel gap (Namatovu & Kanjo, 2019). Health ministries and development agencies have pioneered and supported the development of mobile health applications where local communities are trained to monitor and supervise different health issues in their respective areas. With the use of smartphones, Village Health Teams can monitor malnutrition cases in children, report childbirths and deaths, maternal mortalities, and any other pandemic. The current use of social media by the government through the health department has quickened information transfer in cases of disease outbreaks and management.

Previous research on mHealth has largely focused on evaluating and understanding these formal programmes and pilots (Hampshire et al., 2021). This research has shown how mHealth offers opportunities for improving the management of health information, the coordination of healthcare services, and the delivery of care and treatment. However, research has also drawn attention to the ways in which mHealth may fail to achieve its aims, even exacerbating inequities in the healthcare service. Moreover, while mHealth is becoming increasingly recognized, evidence of scaled-up, sustained initiatives in LMICs are not as well established. This discrepancy is a likely product of a tendency still toward investment in pilots that fail to reach scale (and are not published) without sustained resourcing owing to a lack of longer-term funding arrangements (McCool et al., 2022).

More recently, however, research has begun to show how alongside formal mHealth interventions, patients, health workers and managers are informally using mobile phones to improve healthcare (Miller, D. et al., 2021). The informal use of mobile phones increased further with the the Covid-19 pandemic, when physical distancing was employed as one of several strategies to curb transmission of infection. . The large underserved population in the emerging economies combined with the gaping vacuum in consumer choice for health care during the global Covid-19 pandemic fueled growth in mHealth in LMICs (ref). Covid 19 accelerated the use of mobile phones by health workers and managers with the formalization of, for instance, WhatsApp groups. More research is needed to understand the often creative and innovative process ‘from below’, and to recognize its diverse affordances and challenges.

This project will explore how health workers use mobile phones in informal and creative ways, for instance to communicate with patients under their care; seek practical or technical support for patient management or referral; or obtain emotional and practical support from their peers. By connecting with

the rest of the mHEALTH-INNOVATE project, it will explore how these innovations can be formally integrated within the health system to improve service delivery and ultimately reduce disease burden and promote equity.

Approaches, hypotheses, and choice of method

The overall goal of this PhD project is to explore health workers' and managers' innovative, informal and ad hoc use of mobile phones in Uganda; and draw lessons to address health systems challenges and promote effective and equitable health service delivery.

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Project objectives

- To explore how health workers and managers informally utilise mobile phones in their everyday work
- To establish the unmet needs of health workers and managers that can be addressed by informal and innovative mobile phone use
- To investigate how health workers and managers manage issues related to equity, transparency, patient confidentiality, and documentation of clinical practice while using mobile phones

Theoretical approach

The project will draw on **Normalization Process Theory (NPT)** –NPT focuses on the dynamic processes and practical steps through which complex interventions and technologies are made 'workable' or operationalized (May et al., 2007). It aims to explain how individuals and groups 'normalise' interventions so that they become part of routine practice (Murray et al., 2010). These are described in four determinants: (1) coherence – where the new practice 'makes sense' to the people involved; (2) cognitive participation – where they are engaged and invested in its implementation; (3) collective action – where they are able to work together to make it function; and (4) reflexive monitoring — where they consider the impacts of the practice after using it for a while (Murray et al., 2010). NPT focuses on interventions that aim to 'introduce new, or modify existing, patterns of collective action in health care' (May et al., 2007). NPT is therefore similar to social innovation theory in that both aim to understand the planned and widespread uptake of an innovation, as opposed to more ad hoc and individualized strategies. However, as opposed to social innovation theory and to the focus of this study, NPT is likely to be a useful perspective in helping us think through why formal systems are not always used routinely and why informal systems may be preferred. It can also help us consider the extent to which informal strategies initiated by individual health workers are likely to be taken up by other health workers and also how a particularly informal use spreads and becomes embedded among a group of health workers. The study will also draw upon the literature on Lipsky's 'street-level bureaucrat' concept (Lipsky, 1980) concerned with the interpretation and adoption of practices that are directed from higher levels of the system. As opposed to NPT, however, the focus here is on street level providers' *adoption* of these practices rather than on their successful (or unsuccessful) implementation. Lipsky describes how people working at the interface between citizens and government – including healthcare workers – and who are expected to deliver policies and practices established elsewhere, create their own interpretations, routines and strategies to deliver the services required of them. The study will refer to Lipsky's concept to gain a deeper knowledge on how health workers and their managers have created their own routines and strategies to deliver health services.

Knowledge gap to be filled

Most existing research in digital health, particularly in LMICs, involves the evaluation of formal, top-down digital health programmes. This project will therefore fill an important gap in our knowledge by showing how people are creatively and informally using digital technologies from the bottom-up to help

solve problems in the healthcare system. Drawing on medical anthropology, implementation science, health policy studies and informatics, it will show how new practices are taken up within the health facility and integrated into routine work, and how health workers and managers have urgency to create novel solutions to address their day-to-day challenges. By connecting primary research in Uganda with a systematic review of qualitative studies (as part of another work-package in the mHEALTH-INNOVATE project), the project will also contrast and integrate empirical observations in Uganda with experiences in the settings identified in the review. Overall, high impact empirical contributions will be produced in the field of implementation science to show how self-initiated and informally adapted innovations by health workers become embedded into routine clinical practice, and how the use of such innovations intersects with questions on health systems governance.

Generalization and application of knowledge

The PhD project will take advantage of opportunities for the generalization and application of the knowledge it produces through its connections to the larger mHEALTH-INNOVATE project, specifically work-package 4, ‘Deliberating and co-designing options for integrating informal uses of mobile phone messaging apps with formal digital systems in Uganda, regionally and globally’. Empirical findings will be fed into this work-package through deliberative dialogues with key stakeholders including the WHO and the Ministry of Health in Uganda. By generating new evidence on the informal and innovative use of mobile phone messaging apps by health workers, valuable lessons for strengthening health systems and the promotion of effective and equitable service delivery will be provided. The research will seek to understand and inform the strengthening of health worker performance – a crucial health policy objective in LMICs and one captured by the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in SDG3 target 3.C (“Increase health financing and support health workforce in developing countries”).

Research methods

The PhD candidate will conduct a qualitative study, drawing heavily on ethnographic methodologies, including observation, interviews and focus group discussions with health workers and managers at the facility and district level, as well as village health team members, and other relevant actors. The epistemological approach will be the interpretivist paradigm given the project’s interest in understanding people’s views and experiences concerning how health workers and managers are informally using their mobile phones in their everyday work.

Ethnographic methodologies traditionally rely upon long periods of fieldwork, allowing the PhD candidate to build rapport with the participants in the study area, which is vital in order to explore people's personal experiences and perceptions (Ingold 2008). Drawing on these methodologies will provide opportunities to study people in their everyday lives, where social life is an unfolding process and sequence of interlocking events. This form of research, Maxwell (2013, p. 475) argues, involves “tacking back and forth in the research design.” In this study, the PhD candidate will be actively engaged in dialogue meetings and discussions between health workers, community health workers, managers, patients, district-level leaders, and any other actors. The aim is to get first-hand information from both service delivery personnel, patients and health managers of facilities.

Project area

The research will be conducted in Wakiso and Butambala districts, both in the central region of Uganda. The two districts were purposively selected to represent key criteria for use of mobile phones within the health system including internet connectivity, availability of electricity, and ownership of mobile phones. Wakiso with a population of approximately 87,900 people, hosts Kira, Uganda’s second-largest largest city. Wakiso district was selected to represent an urban district, with high use of digital technology and

good internet connectivity. Butambala district was selected to represent a district that is largely rural, with a likely high need for health workers and patients to use their mobile telephone to access health services.

Within each of these districts, the project will sample three health centres (level four and three facilities) for the study. In the Ugandan health system, health facilities are categorized according to the level of care and range of services available. Health Centre (level II-IV) found at the parish, county, and sub-county level provide promotive, preventive, and curative services. Hospitals at the district, regional and national levels provide the full range of services, specialist care as well as research and training of health workers. This study will be conducted at health Centre level IV and III because there is a wide range of healthcare services provided, a large volume of patients, and the long-term employment of health workers which increases the likelihood of recruiting eligible participants for this study.

Target population and sampling

The primary focus of this project are the health workers and the other people they are in communication with using their mobile telephones. Health workers communicate with patients under their care, or individuals in the community, for instance Village Health Team members, or community leaders. They also communicate with other work colleagues in different departments, for instance with pharmacy or laboratory services, or with their managers. Health workers could also communicate with other health workers at higher levels of care, or as part of a WhatsApp group, and even wider networks of professionals. This project will therefore sample health workers and using a snowballing approach, select participants from others they are in communication with including patients, community health workers, other health workers at the health facility and district level managers. If possible, the PhD candidate will seek to embed herself in one of the networks the selected health worker is using to communicate with others. A purposive sample of health workers or managers that actively communicate with their mobile phones will be used to identify app-based networks of health workers, and to obtain permission to invite network members to be study participants in each district.

Data collection methods

A range of data collection methods will be used to cross-validate and capture different dimensions of the phenomenon being researched:

- 1. Observations of health workers:** The project will observe health workers carrying out their daily work activities, with a focus on their use of mobile phones. Notes will be taken of the observations, including information about the type of activity the health worker is involved in (for instance patient consultations, stock notifications, staff meetings); the extent to which the health worker uses his or her mobile phone; and the reasons for this use. To gain access to the field site and build rapport with often overburdened health workers, the PhD candidate will, with authorisation from relevant authorities, offer support for strictly non-medical administrative tasks, such as assisting with the patient flow in the waiting room.
- 2. Observations of health worker app communication:** Through discussions with health workers who have agreed to participate in the project, the PhD candidate will identify messaging app-based networks that they belong to and use to communicate with others about work-related topics. These include, for instance, WhatsApp groups, where members include other health workers, managers, supervisors, or patients. Permission to observe these groups will be requested. With the help of our health worker participants, the project will contact the administrator of the network they belong to and request permission to observe the group. If the administrator agrees, the administrator will notify all

group members about the purpose of the research, and their rights as research participants, and will ask their permission to allow the PhD candidate to join the group and observe their discussions.

- i. The administrator will ask members to privately communicate with the administrator within one week if they do not wish to participate in the research.
- ii. If any member of the group does not want to participate, the PhD candidate will not join the group.
- iii. If there are no objections from any member of the group, the PhD candidate will join the group for a period of up to eight weeks.
- iv. Notes will be taken about issues relevant to the research project, including the range of issues discussed and how health workers manage privacy and confidentiality issues if and when they discuss individual patients.
- v. The PhD candidate will also participate in the groups where appropriate, probing and asking for clarification
- vi. Where notes are made about members of the group or of people they refer to, there will be an anonymisation of any personal data, including names, locations, and the name of the health facility.
- vii. The PhD candidate will post a message to all group members, informing them once the observation period is over.

3. Interviews with health workers: Semi-structured, individual or group interviews will be carried out with health workers and managers at health facilities as well as with selected members of the district health team. These data collection methods will target front-line health workers, for instance in outpatient departments because they are likely to have regular contact with their patients, other health workers and managers at different levels of the health system, including for, managing medicines and supplies. All interviews will be audio-recorded and transcribed.

4. Focus group discussions with health workers: To further explore health workers informal utilisation of mobile phones, the research project will carry out focus group discussions with health workers, and will involve probing further on issues relating to privacy and documentation of clinical practice. Focus group discussions will be audio-recorded and transcribed.

5. Interviews with patients: The research project will also include semi-structured interviews with patients or caregivers who have received services at the health facilities that are being observed. The project will primarily select patients who have been in contact with health workers that have used their mobile phone during their consultation. Interviews will be audio-recorded and transcribed.

Data analysis:

Drawing on street-level bureaucrat theory and normalization process theory as a starting point, and by using framework analysis approach, both inductive and deductive approaches will be used in the data analysis (Ritchie 1994). This will involve a process of re-reading data, developing and finalising codes, and searching for emerging patterns and themes from the data (Braun and Clarke 2008).

4. The project plan, project management, supervisory team, cooperation and organisation
This three-year PhD research project is one of the work-packages (WP2) of the larger mHEALTH-INNOVATE project that is funded by the Norwegian Research Council. The PhD candidate will be based at Makerere University, and will be supported by a supervisory team from the University of Oslo, Makerere University, and Western Norway University of Applied Sciences.

The project’s key milestones are outlined in table 1. In summary, the project will involve a pre-fieldwork period involving a literature review and participation, in a minimal capacity, in a systematic review (this forms a work-package of mHEALTH-INNOVATE project). Following this, fieldwork will be conducted in Uganda for 8 months, after which follows a stage of analysis and writing.

Table 1. Timeline of milestones and key deliverables																
	2022				2023				2024				2025			
Work package and deliverables	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
Ugandan qualitative study																
1.1 Protocol development / ethics approval in Uganda																
1.2 Literature review																
1.3 Develop data collection tools																
1.4 Pilot test and review of data collection tools																
1.5 Data collection: interviews /observations / FGDs																
1.6 Data analysis																
1.7 Draft and submit manuscripts																
1.7 Draft and submit PhD thesis																

As part of the mHEALTH INNOVATE project, this project will be supported by national and international research experts in the project team as well as an international advisory panel. This project will participate in scheduled discussions with the multidisciplinary team of experts where the scope of this research will be clarified, and advise on any methodological or practical challenges will be sought. The PhD candidate will also participate in mHEALTH-INNOVATE project activities in Norway, Uganda and online. These include deliberative dialogues with policy-makers (WP3) and the systematic review (WP1), which will offer the candidate opportunities to build networks with relevant academic and policy-making actors.

Risks

Two key risks have been identified, along with strategies to mitigate them.

- 1, A difficulty in obtaining permission to observe WhatsApp groups or to conduct observations at healthcare facilities. The PhD candidate’s prior networks and experience conducting research in Uganda will help to mitigate this risk. The candidate will also be able to draw on the learnings from a similar pilot research project in South Africa that has been implemented by the mHEALTH-INNOVATE project.
2. The COVID-19 pandemic presents a threat to the implementation of this project, for instance if face to face meetings or interviews are not possible, or if key project members are assigned to other tasks. This will be mitigated by using telephone or online interviews in case face to face interviews are not possible; and drawing on the broader project team to support specific tasks in case any key member is assigned to other tasks.

5. Ethical perspectives

This PhD research project has been submitted, as part of a wider application of the mHEALTH-INNOVATE project, to the Norwegian Regional Ethics Committee (REK) for ethical approval. The PhD candidate is in the process of acquiring all the necessary research clearances and introductory letters from the concerned authorities in Uganda, including Makerere University Social Sciences Research and Ethics committee, and Uganda National Council of Science and Technology.

Project data collection activities will only commence once all clearance from relevant authorities has been granted.

Research that involves mobile phones and internet-based data pose various ethics and regulatory challenges at the national, community or individual levels (Ali J, et al., 2017), including data protection, privacy, and informed consent. The project will follow the Uganda National Council of Science and Technology (UNCST), guidelines for conducting research involving human subjects (2014), on informed consent process, and taking into consideration rights of participants and protecting the vulnerable. In addition, it will follow guidance on internet research ethics provided by the Norwegian Regional Ethics Committee. Conversely, care will be taken to put into consideration the norms and requirements associated with ethics, such as consent for participation, while aligning it with local cultural and regulatory expectations.

The project will ensure that its activities do not pose whatsoever any physical, emotional, or threats compromising the life of the subjects involved. In this case, consent either orally or in writing shall be obtained first from the potential respondent after briefing him or her about the purpose of carrying out a given data collection activity. In so doing, an emphasis and assurance will be given that, the data collection activity will not compromise his/her privacy and confidentiality, nor will undermine his/her dignity. It will be emphasized to the respondents that participating in the project is voluntary and thus, have a right at any point of withdrawing their participation. The PhD candidate is aware of the ethical challenges that might arise when researching informal behaviours. For example, some patients, health workers (participants) might be known to the candidate. Consequently, this will be mitigated by preserving participants' anonymity and ensuring data confidentiality.

There are several more specific actions that will be undertaken and considerations that will be taken into account.

i) It is possible that the research will uncover health worker's practices that may improve health service delivery but that also threaten patient privacy and data security, for instance, health worker practices that involve the sharing of patient information through informal and unregulated digital channels. These practices may also go against current government regulations. The project will, therefore, secure health worker's anonymity in order to protect them from any repercussions, for instance, health workers' places of work and districts will be anonymized to protect their identity. Any information about individual patients gathered through observations or interviews will also be anonymized. In addition, the project will actively explore technical and organizational solutions to problems identified when health workers use digital platforms, including problems tied to patient information privacy

ii) When observing health workers' use of their mobile telephones, the PhD candidate will inevitably observe or record information about patients' health. This makes it necessary to secure the patients' informed consent and ensure anonymity and confidentiality. If the health workers carry out patient (or caregiver) consultations during these observations, informed consent will also be secured from these patients. There will only be observation of patients that have provided consent away from the health

worker, for instance, outside in the waiting room. Where notes are made about individual patients, there will be an anonymization of any personal data, including their name, their location, and the name of the healthcare facility.

iii) One part of the project is to observe health worker communication on messaging app networks such as WhatsApp groups. These types of networks have become increasingly popular during the Covid-19 pandemic, but there are concerns about confidentiality when patient information is shared in these groups. However, as some groups have several hundred members, it will be difficult to achieve informed consent from every group member, particularly as many may not be active members and may be difficult to contact. An approach (as described above) has been devised which will work to ensure the welfare and integrity of each participant. This includes only observing groups where no member has declined, note-taking rather than recording or downloading group chats, and anonymizing any personal information during notetaking. The project shall also work closely with social media administrators specifically administrators of different WhatsApp groups to seek consent from the members of the forum.

6. Dissemination and communication of results

The main target audiences include health policy and systems researchers, policymakers, international and regional health and non-governmental organizations, health worker's organisations and the research participants themselves. Beyond journal article publications, and as part of the broader project, the PhD candidate will use several channels and approaches to communicate findings to these audiences and to facilitate uptake of these findings by health systems strengthening initiatives.

The main activities for reaching target audiences, which also are part of other work-packages in the larger project, include: (1) dissemination meetings for research participants at health facilities, (2) stakeholder panel discussions, deliberative dialogues and moderated discussions. Participants in the deliberative dialogues will include: government ministries and authorities in Uganda, including the Ministry of Health, Department of Health Information and Management System; Ministry of ICT and National Guidance; The National Information Technology Authority; and the Uganda Communications Commission; International organizations including the WHO and the Healthcare Information for All (HIFA) network; (3) seminars at Makerere and online, including with WHO EMRO and with WHO HQ; (4) presentations at academic conferences; (5) user-friendly summaries and evidence briefs distributed through newsletters, project and partner websites, and social media channels of partner institutions and other relevant networks; and (6) information through messaging app networks identified through the project.

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